

***Dynastes septentrionalis* Lachaume, 1985
(Coleoptera: Scarabaeidae: Dynastinae) in Guatemala:
Male morphological variation, distribution, and ecological notes**

José MONZÓN-SIERRA¹ and Richard S. ZACK^{2*}

¹Centro de Estudios Ambientales y Biodiversidad, Universidad del Valle de Guatemala, 18 Avenida 11-95 Zona 15, Vista Hermosa III, Guatemala, Guatemala

²Department of Entomology, M. T. James Entomological Collection, Washington State University, Pullman, Washington 99164-6382, U.S.A.

*Corresponding author. E-mail: zack@wsu.edu

Abstract. The Hercules beetle, *Dynastes septentrionalis* Lachaume, 1985 is distributed throughout much of Mesoamerica. One-hundred forty-six specimens from Guatemala (105 males and 41 females) were studied to establish distribution and male morphological variation. Males ranging from 58 to 140 mm in length were examined for morphological variation. Specimens were collected at 26 locations in Alta Verapaz, Baja Verapaz, El Progreso, Huehuetenango, Izabal, Quiché, and Zacapa Departments. The species was found mainly on the north-facing slopes of the Sierra Madre and several of its branches. Specimens were collected in tropical moist and wet forests at altitudes ranging from 10 to 2033 m above sea level. We also present an atypical habitat record for a female collected at the Reserva de Biósfera Sierra de Las Minas in a pine forest in August 2024. This is well outside the normal ranges of forest type and elevation.

Resumen. El escarabajo Hércules, *Dynastes septentrionalis* Lachaume, 1985 se distribuye en la mayor parte de Mesoamérica. Se estudiaron ciento cuarenta y seis ejemplares (105 machos y 41 hembras) para establecer la distribución y la variación morfológica de los machos. Se examinó la variación morfológica de ejemplares machos de entre 58 y 140 mm de largo. Ejemplares fueron colectados en 26 localidades en los departamentos de Alta Verapaz, Baja Verapaz, El Progreso, Huehuetenango, Izabal, Quiché y Zacapa. La especie se encontró principalmente en la vertiente norte de la Sierra Madre y varias de sus ramas. Ejemplares se colectaron en bosques tropicales húmedos y muy húmedos en alturas que oscilan entre 10 y 2033 metros sobre el nivel del mar. También presentamos un registro ecológico atípico de una hembra colectada en la Reserva de Biósfera Sierra de Las Minas en un bosque de Pino en agosto 2024. Este registro esta fuera de los rangos normales del tipo de bosque y altitud.

Keywords. Central America, ecology, Hercules beetle, Mesoamerica

Palabras Clave. Centro América, ecología, escarabajo Hércules, Mesoamérica

INTRODUCTION

Hercules beetles are among the most famous and sought after insects in the world. Males of some species have very well-developed and showy horns that are used for fighting with other males. The common name Hercules beetle usually refers to the genus *Dynastes*, which currently comprizes 15 species (Huang 2017). In Guatemala, two species, *Dynastes maya* Hardy, 2003 and *Dynastes septentrionalis* Lachaume, 1985 occur (Huang 2017). Studies of these giant beetles (including *D. septentrionalis*) have mostly been limited to alpha taxonomy and some aspects of morphology, whereas geographic distribution has been generalized (Morón 2009). Many specimens of Hercules beetles have been made available through commercial collectors, who often generalize or provide false locality information to protect their collecting sites. Specimens collected by researchers and private collectors who provide exact data are less common; thus, detailed published information is limited.

Nomenclature for species in this genus has been confusing, as many names have been used to designate species and subspecies based on morphological differences, especially in the male horns. For example, Ratcliffe et al. (2013) used the name *Dynastes hercules septentrionalis* Lachaume, 1985 for the Central American species in their treatise “The Dynastine Scarab Beetles of Mexico, Guatemala, and Belize (Coleoptera: Scarabaeidae: Dynastinae)”, while in a previous book (Ratcliffe 2003) he designated it as *Dynastes hercules* (Linnaeus, 1758). The latest synopsis of the genus (Huang 2017) has served to stabilize the taxonomy of the genus and gives full species status to many previously designated subspecies, including *D. septentrionalis*.

Dynastes septentrionalis is distributed from southern Mexico to Panama, where it inhabits lowland and montane broadleaf forests (Fig. 1) at elevations between 500 and 2000 m (Ratcliffe et al. 2013, Huang 2017). In Guatemala, most of the specimens collected and available to us came from Izabal Department, where they were collected with light traps (Fig. 2, 3). The type locality for *D. septentrionalis* is Quixal, Alta Verapaz in Guatemala, and the holotype is deposited in the Muséum National d’Histoire Naturelle in Paris (Huang 2017) (see specimen from type locality Fig. 4). Most of the specimens recorded in the literature for this species are from Guatemala (118) followed by Costa Rica (79), Panama (57), Honduras (44), Nicaragua (11), México (8), and Belize (5) (Ratcliffe 2003, Ratcliffe & Cave 2006, Ratcliffe et al. 2013). Morón (2009) provided an excellent account of previous work and knowledge for this species.

The information published on *D. septentrionalis* from Guatemala is limited. The most complete accounting is Ratcliffe et al. (2013) where they provided a list of localities in which the species was collected as well as distribution maps. Ratcliffe et al. (2013) also provided accounts of nomenclatural issues, especially as they concern subspecies, and a nice discussion of natural history details.

The shape of the male horns has been used as an important character to identify Hercules beetles, although the large amount of variation has caused significant confusion. In Central America, *D. septentrionalis* is the only species in the “Giant Hercules beetles” group (Huang 2017), and studying the variation with the certainty that there is only one species in the group in Guatemala allows us to more easily study morphological diversity. There has also been confusion in separating medium-sized males of *D. septentrionalis* from those of *Dynastes maya* Hardy, 2003 (“White Hercules beetles” group (Huang 2017)) based on cephalic horn denticles. Nevertheless, separating males of these two species relies on the row of reddish-brown setae along the elytral suture, which are lacking in *D. maya* (Ratcliffe et al. 2013).

The primary objective of this study is to provide precise information on the distribution and morphology of *D. septentrionalis* in Guatemala. Most of the specimens examined by Ratcliffe et al. (2013) are from the José Monzón Private Collection, currently in the process of being accessioned into the Universidad del Valle de Guatemala Arthropod Collection (UVGC). In this paper, we add to the information provided by Ratcliffe et al. (2013) in terms of geographic (Appendix 3) and elevational details (Fig. 22). We also provide a detailed account of cephalic horn morphology and provide an unusual ecological record that extends the elevational distribution and forest type for the species.

The specimens examined in this study were mostly collected by the first author during a period that spans more than 30 years (since 1991). Although the collecting was not systematic, the large number of specimens analyzed (more than 140) provided significant information on *D. septentrionalis* in Guatemala. More than 100 specimens

Figures 1–3. *Dynastes septentrionalis* habitat and collecting method. 1) Premontane moist forest, a low cloud forest, where *D. septentrionalis* is a common species at Reserva Hídrica y Forestal Sierra de Caral, Morales, Izabal, a FUNDAECO protected reserve on the border with Honduras; 2) FUNDAECO conservation organization headquarters at Reserva Hídrica y Forestal Sierra de Caral, with light trap, a good place to collect *D. septentrionalis*; 3) Light trap where *D. septentrionalis* specimens were collected, Finca Firmeza, Sierra de Caral, 1050 m, Izabal.

came from the Caral Mountains (Fig. 5), an area in which, during these years, we had full elevational access for collecting between 200 and 1200 m. The accumulated material from this wide elevational transect provided a very good idea of the elevational preferences of the species. Most of the specimens examined in this study are

Figures 4, 5. *Dynastes septentrionalis* specimens. 4) Major male specimen from the type locality, Quixal, July 2007; 5) Male specimens from Finca Firmeza, Sierra de Caral, July 2007.

males (105 specimens), usually collected because of their stunning and variable horns. Females are relatively simple and invariant, as they do not have thoracic or cephalic horns (Fig. 6).

METHODS AND MATERIALS

This study is based on the examination of 146 specimens (105 males and 41 females, Appendices 1 & 2) of *D. septentrionalis* from 26 localities in seven departments of Guatemala. Specimens were identified by the authors using Huang (2017) and Ratcliffe et al. (2013). These specimens were used to produce the distribution map (Fig. 21). The majority of specimens examined were collected by the first author during a period of more than 30 years, beginning 13 August 1991. Most of the specimens were collected at light traps in nonsystematic collecting trips to accessible areas suitable for this species. Typical light-trap setups included a 400- or 250-watt metal halide lamp and a 15- or 20-watt ultraviolet (UV) light tube (Fig. 2, 3). A small percentage of specimens was collected by local people where light sources were close to the forest, including for example, at the type locality of the species, Quixal (a hydroelectric plant), or Cerro San Gil where there are radio antennas.

Terminology on male morphology follows Huang (2017). Ecological information follows Pérez-Irungaray et al. (2018). Photographs of specimens were taken with a

Figures 6–9. *Dynastes septentrionalis* specimens. 6) Female specimen from San Lorenzo, Reserva de Biósfera Sierra de Las Minas, 2033 m, pine forest, an unusual ecological record; 7) Minor male with reduced thoracic and cephalic armature; 8) Medium male with typical armature configuration for the species; 9) Major male with typical armature configuration.

Canon R7 camera and RF 100-mm 2.8L macro IS USM lens in a light box. Drawings of the distribution map and specimens were produced in Adobe Illustrator (several versions). Specimens were measured with a standard Vernier caliper in millimeters.

Specimens cited and/or examined are deposited in the following collections:

- UVGC Universidad del Valle de Guatemala Collection of Arthropods, Guatemala City, Guatemala
- MDPC Maishe Dickman Private Collection, New Haven, Connecticut, U.S.A.
- WSUC M. T. James Entomological Collection at Washington State University, Pullman, Washington, U.S.A.

RESULTS

Male Morphological Variation. Male *D. septentrionalis* in Guatemala are large beetles (Fig. 7–9), which, in our study, averaged 101 mm in length. Length of specimens ranged from 58 to 140 mm. The typical form has a long thoracic horn with two basal teeth and a long cephalic horn with a medial and preapical tooth (Fig. 8, 9, 13, 20). Most variation is found on the cephalic horn, which varies in length and has different numbers of teeth and denticles (Fig. 10–20). For the purposes of this study, we divided

Figures 10–20. *Dynastes septentrionalis* from Guatemala male variation. 10–12) Minor males with simple armature; 13) Medium size male with typical male horn configuration; 14) Medium size male with very simple cephalic horn armature, no medial and apical tooth and no denticles; 15) Medium male with cephalic medial tooth very reduced; 16) Medium male preapical tooth fused with several denticles; 17) Medium male with complex cephalic horn armature, large medial and preapical teeth plus denticle; 18) Major male with no cephalic medial tooth; 19) Major male with complex cephalic horn armature, large medial and preapical teeth plus several denticles; 20) Large major male with typical horn configuration.

males into three categories based on size: minor males with a length of 58–80 mm (23% of the sample) (Fig. 7, 10–12); medium males 81–110 mm (35%) (Fig. 8, 13–17); and major males with a length of 111–140 mm (42%) (Fig. 4, 5, 9, 18–20). Major males show the least variation in horn morphology, with 80% of the sampled specimens having the typical form. Medium males show more variation with 58% having the typical form. None of the minor males are of the typical form, as most lack the medial, preapical or both teeth on the cephalic horn. Although we did not analyze correlations statistically, we did not see an evident association between variations in horn length and structure with variables such as forest type, time of year, and climate among the many that could be analyzed.

Minor males (Fig. 7, 10–12) exhibit simplified thoracic and cephalic horn structures (Fig. 10–12). Twenty-four minor males were examined with body lengths between 58 and 80 mm (Appendix 1). All of these specimens have reduced thoracic and cephalic armature with few (reduced) or no denticles (Table 1). Seven of the specimens have medium-sized thoracic teeth (29%), whereas the remainder (71%) have them very reduced or absent. One specimen (4%) has one extra denticle; 19 have the medial cephalic tooth very reduced or absent (79%) and all specimens lack the preapical cephalic tooth.

The armature of medium-sized males (Fig. 8, 13–17) is the most complex, with 42% of the specimens showing some type of variation in relation to the typical form of the species. Thirty-six males were examined (Appendix 1), with lengths between 81 and 110 mm (Table 1). Nine specimens have medium-sized basal thoracic teeth (25%), and two specimens have basal teeth reduced or absent (6%). Nine specimens have extra cephalic denticles (25%); three have reduced or absent medial cephalic teeth (8%); and eight specimens have a reduced or absent preapical cephalic tooth (22%).

Major males (Fig. 4, 5, 9, 18–20) can be very large and have very impressive armature; most show the characteristics of the typical form (80%) (Table 1). Forty-four specimens were examined with lengths between 111 and 140 mm. All specimens have well-developed basal teeth on the thoracic horn and medial teeth on the cephalic horn.

Table 1. Size and morphological characters of *Dynastes septentrionalis* males.

#	Length (mm)	Typical form #	Thoracic horn			Cephalic horn	
			Basal tooth medium sized	Basal tooth reduced or absent	1–7 extra denticles	Medial tooth reduced or absent	Preapical tooth reduced or absent
Minor males							
3	50–60	0	1	2	0	3	3
8	61–70	0	0	8	0	8	8
13	71–80	0	6	7	1	8	13
Medium males							
9	81–90	5	1	1	1	1	4
17	91–100	11	7	1	3	2	2
11	101–110	6	1	0	5	0	1
Major males							
20	111–120	15	0	0	4	0	1
24	121–140	20	0	0	4	0	0

Eight specimens (18%) have an irregular cephalic horn surface with one to four extra, often very small, denticles, and one specimen (2%) has a very reduced medial tooth (Fig. 18).

Distribution and Ecology. In general, the species inhabits forest habitats on the northern slopes of the Sierra Madre and its different branches, especially close to or facing the Caribbean Sea (Fig. 1). The species was described from specimens from Quixal, Alta Verapaz Department (type locality) in the municipality of San Cristobal Verapaz (Huang 2017). We examined seven specimens from this locality, Sierra Panpacché in central Guatemala, in the southwestern part of the department (Fig. 22, locality #2). One hundred three specimens (Appendices 1, 2) were collected in the Sierra del Merendón, Izabal department, in the easternmost part of the country, close to the border with Honduras. Another important collecting area is Cerro San Gil, the closest mountains to the Caribbean Sea, near Amatique Bay, from which we analyzed 12 specimens. Other specimens (Fig. 21) were collected from the following departments: Izabal (5) and the northern slopes of the mountains in Huehuetenango (4), Quiché (4), Alta Verapaz (2), Baja Verapaz (6), and Zacapa (1).

Specimens of *D. septentrionalis* have been collected in Guatemala in tropical moist or wet forests at elevations between near sea level (10 m) and 2033 m as follows: tropical moist forest 88 specimens (61%); premontane moist forest 35 specimens (24%); premontane wet forest 21 specimens (14%), and tropical wet forest one specimen (1%). Most of the specimens (78) were collected at elevations between 801 and 1000 m (55%). The second elevational interval with the second most specimens (29) is 1001–1200 m (20%) and the third is 401–600 m with 13 specimens (9%). The preferred elevational range for this species in Guatemala is between 401 and 1200 m, with 85% of all collected specimens (121). Intervals of 0–200 m, 201–400 m, and 1401–1600 m have fewer collected specimens with only 5–7 (4–5%). Specimens from other elevational intervals, especially above 1600 m, are very scarce, averaging less than one specimen each (Fig. 23). Of the 146 specimens examined, 139 had label data indicating date of capture. No specimens were collected during the months of January, March, September, November, or December. Months with the most specimens reported are July with 49 specimens (35%), June with 33 (24%), May with 27 (19%), and August with 17 (12%). The months with the fewest records are April with 9 specimens (6%), February with 2 (1%), and October with 2 (1%).

Atypical Ecological Report. The forest types in which *D. septentrionalis* is found are usually tropical moist or wet forests, especially from low- and middle-elevation cloud forests. The following record of a female (Fig. 6) represents a very interesting ecological report, as it is a specimen taken at the highest elevation recorded for the species in Guatemala and in a mostly rather dry pine forest usually not associated as the habitat for this species: “GUATEMALA, Zacapa | San Lorenzo, Camino mar- | molera a Cerro Monos | 2033 m. 7–9 agosto 2024 | 15.104559 –90.67.6924 | J. Monzón y F. Camposeco.”

DISCUSSION

Dynastes septentrionalis has one of the largest ranges among the Hercules beetles, from Tuxtla Gutiérrez in Veracruz state in south-central Mexico through Guatemala and all of Central America to Panama (Huang 2017). It is less common in the northernmost part of its range. In Mexico, it is known by very few specimens, with

Figure 21. *Dynastes septentrionalis* collecting localities in Guatemala. Yellow circles with numbers: 1 Rubelsanto, 2 (white star) Quixal, type locality; 3 San Cristóbal Verapaz, 4 Finca Saboj, Tres Cruces; 5 Finca Linda Vista, Pansal; 6 Hotel Ranchitos del Quetzal, 7 San Lorenzo, 8 Unión Las Palmas, 9 Nuevo San Mateo, 10 Río Zarco, El Arenal; 11 Cerro San Gil, 12 Mariscos town, 13 Finca Firmeza, 450 m; 14 Finca Firmeza, 600 m; 15 Finca Firmeza, 700 m; 16 Finca Firmeza, logging camp; 17 Finca Firmeza, 1,000 m; 18 Finca Firmeza, 1050 m; 19 Finca Firmeza, 1200 m; 20 Reserva Hídrica y Forestal Sierra de Caral, 21 Close to Negro Norte, 1000 m; 22 Close to Negro Norte, 1150 m; 23 Sierra Caral, 24 Finca San Francisco, 25 Cuatro Chorros, Cerro Amay; 26 La Unión. Areas of interest to search for *D. septentrionalis* (Orange circles): A Parque Nacional Sierra del Lacandón, B Maya Mountains, C eastern middle and lowlands of Alta Verapaz department, C Santa Cruz Mountains in Izabal department, and E northern slopes of Reserva de Biósfera Sierra de Las Minas.

a dozen or so reported from the area of Comitán in Chiapas (Bolivar et al. 1963). The northernmost report for the species is 400 km northwest of the Comitán site near Tuxtla Gutiérrez, from where Morón (1993) described *Dynastes hercules tuxtlaensis* Moron, 1993 from two specimens. This subspecies was synonymized with

Figure 22. Elevational distribution of *Dynastes septentrionalis* in Guatemala.

D. hercules septentrionalis by Ratcliffe et al. (2013) and *D. septentrionalis* by Huang (2017). The two specimens used to describe this subspecies are consistent with the series of *D. septentrionalis* presented in this publication, as minor males with very simple armature.

In Guatemala, *D. septentrionalis* appears to be dependent on particular ecological conditions. It was found in a wide range of elevations, forest types, and climatic conditions but is rarely collected in circumstances other than very humid or wet tropical forests in low cloud forest habitats, where it can be common. For example, at Ranchitos del Quetzal lodge (1600 m, Purulhá, Baja Verapaz) where the native forest is in very good condition, only one specimen was collected in hundreds of total nights of light trapping. In contrast, in areas of lower forests with elevations between 800 and 1250 m, such as the Caral Mountains on the border with Honduras, up to 16 specimens have been found at a single light trap in one night. Based on our observations, the relative low abundance of *D. septentrionalis* in Guatemala is due to the lack of human access to appropriate habitats for the species. The prime localities where they were previously collected (mainly the Caral Mountains and Cerro San Gil in Izabal) are no longer accessible, at least to the best elevations where they occur. This area was a logging camp that was accessible, but logging has ceased and roads have disappeared. Other areas where they should be somewhat abundant are ecologically compromised to such a degree that populations must be extremely low or have disappeared. For example, most of Alta Verapaz Department would have provided excellent habitat for *D. septentrionalis*, but most of its forest has been replaced by pine, coffee or corn plantations.

The finding of a female *D. septentrionalis* at an elevation of 2033 m is very important. Only two specimens (1.4% of the sample) have been collected above 1600 m, and this is the only one above 2000 m. Also having been collected in a dry pine forest represents valuable information and brings up some interesting thoughts. First, is there a

viable population living in this kind of forest? It seems very unlikely that this ecosystem would have enough suitable food for larvae of this species, which may take up to three years to develop to adults (JM-S, personal observation; see Ratcliffe et al. 2013 for additional developmental information). If there is a viable population in this habitat, do larvae feed on pine wood? This is unlikely, although *Dynastes tityus* (Linnaeus, 1763) from North America has been found feeding on pine (Quinn 2008). Large oaks and other trees occur in the area, but they are very uncommon.

Variation in horn morphology among all sizes is a constant in the species. Minor males have simpler armature, as expected. Thoracic tooth and simple cephalic horn configurations with fewer extra denticles and reduced medial and preapical teeth are common. About half of the medium-sized males examined have the typical horn configuration for the species. Very few have a middle tooth, and fewer still have a reduced preapical tooth. Most major males have the typical horn configuration, with all specimens examined having normal thoracic horns. Only one specimen had a reduced cephalic preapical tooth, and 18% have extra denticles. The longest Guatemalan specimen is 140 mm long, close to the maximum (145 mm) reported for the species (Chalumeau & Reid 2002). See Emlen et al. (2007) for an excellent discussion of horn variation and its modulation.

No natural history information has been reported for this species in Guatemala beyond what is presented in this paper. Most of the information comes from non-systematic sampling, and many questions remain. More research is needed to better understand the species in Guatemala, and systematic collecting at specific localities is advised.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This study was made possible by the generous support of the people of the United States, through the United States Agency for International Development (USAID). The content is the responsibility of Fundación Defensores de la Naturaleza (FDN) and Universidad del Valle de Guatemala (UVG) and does not necessarily reflect the views of USAID or the United States Government. We would like to thank the Centro de Estudios Ambientales y Biodiversidad (Universidad del Valle de Guatemala) for support, especially Daniel Ariano, Gabriela Alfaro, Gabriela Fuentes, and Jiichiro Yoshimoto (all Guatemala, Guatemala). CONAP (Consejo Nacional de Áreas Protegidas) supported our research with research permit license DVCB-16-2024). Many people have helped to gather the data presented in this paper. We are especially grateful to: Fundación Defensores de la Naturaleza, Fundación para el Ecodesarrollo y la Conservación (FUNDAECO) (Guatemala, Guatemala), Alexis Cerezo (Guatemala, Guatemala), Javier Márquez (Guatemala, Guatemala), Luis Trujillo (Guatemala, Guatemala), Elder Pérez (Morales, Guatemala), Rolando Gómez (Huehuetenango, Guatemala), Cristina Abugarade (Guatemala, Guatemala), Maishe Dickman (New Haven, Connecticut), Robert E. Woodruff (deceased, Gainesville, Florida), Faustino Camposeco (Huehuetenango, Guatemala), Rocío León (Guatemala, Guatemala), Edgar Alfredo Mó (Cobán, Guatemala), Andrés Pérez (Yepocapa, Guatemala), Jorge Luis Ramírez (Chilasco, Guatemala), Neal Mower (deceased, Ivins, Utah), Kenneth C. Smith (Scottsdale, Arizona), Gary Wilson (Douglas, Isle of Man), Paul Holt (Newark, England), and Howard Romack (Cambridge, New York). Special thanks to Robert W. Sites (Columbia, Missouri), José Francisco García (Santa Elena,

Guatemala), and three anonymous reviewers for providing valuable feedback for the improvement of the manuscript.

LITERATURE CITED

- Bolívar, C., L. Jiménez-Asúa & A. Martínez. 1963. Notas sobre Dynastinae neotropicales con especial referencia a especies Mexicanas. *Ciencia (México)* 22(6):181–190.
- Chalumeau, F. & W. Reid. 2002. Aperçus sur le complexe *hercules* et. Statut du *Dynastes Alcides* (Coleoptera, Dynastidae). *Nouvelle Revue d'Entomologie (N.S.)* 19:83–91.
- Emlen, D. J., L. C. Lavine & B. Ewen-Campen. 2007. On the origin and evolutionary diversification of beetle horns. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 104(Supplement 1):8661–8668. <http://www.pnas.org/cgi/doi/10.1073/pnas.0701209104>.
- Huang, H. P. 2017. The Hercules beetles (subgenus *Dynastes*, genus *Dynastes*, Dynastidae): A revisionary study based on the integration of molecular, morphological, ecological, and geographic analyses. *Miscellaneous Publications Museum of Zoology, University of Michigan* 206:1–31.
- Morón, M. A. 1993. Nueva subespecie Mexicana de *Dynastes hercules* (L.) (Coleoptera: Melolonthidae: Dynastinae). *Giornale Italiano di Entomologia* 6:257–262.
- Morón, M. A. 2009. El género *Dynastes* MacLeay, 1819 en la Zona de Transición Mexicana (Coleoptera: Melolonthidae: Dynastinae). *Boletín Sociedad Entomológica Aragonesa* 45:23–38.
- Pérez-Irungaray, G. E., J. C. Rosito-Monzón, R. E. Maas-Ibarra & G. A. Gándara-Cabrera. 2018. *Ecosistemas de Guatemala Basado en el Sistema de Clasificación de Zonas de Vida*. IARNA, Guatemala, Guatemala, 122 pp.
- Quinn, M. 2008. Texas Beetle Information. Available from: <https://www.texasento.net/Dynastes.htm> (accessed 20 February 2025).
- Ratcliffe, B. C. 2003. The dynastine scarab beetles of Costa Rica and Panama (Coleoptera: Scarabaeidae: Dynastinae). *Bulletin of the University of Nebraska State Museum* 16:1–506.
- Ratcliffe, B. C. & R. D. Cave. 2006. The dynastine scarab beetles of Honduras, Nicaragua, and El Salvador. *Bulletin of the University of Nebraska State Museum* 21:1–424.
- Ratcliffe, B. C., R. D. Cave & E. B. Cano. 2013. The dynastine scarab beetles of Mexico, Guatemala and Belize (Coleoptera: Scarabaeidae: Dynastinae). *Bulletin of the University of Nebraska State Museum* 27:1–661.

Received 8 Aug 2025; accepted 8 Nov 2025. Publication date 31 December 2025

Subject editor Jason A. Hansen

Appendix 1. Male specimens of *Dynastes septentrionalis* examined in this study. Code: JMS = José Monzón Sierra; UVGC = Universidad del Valle de Guatemala Arthropod Collection; WSUC = Washington State University Collection; EA Mó = report from Edgar Alfredo Mó; MDPC = Maishe Dickman Private Collection; Wilson = Gary Wilson.

Specimen #	Code	Locality	Elevation (m)	Date	Length (mm)
Alta Verapaz Department					
1	JMS10620	Rubelsanto	140	No data	126
2	JMS10554	Quixal	400	14 April 2007	111
3	JMS10565	Quixal	400	15 April 2007	122
4	UVGC0010217	Quixal	400	1998	99
5	UVGC0010219	Quixal	400	1998	100
Baja Verapaz Department					
6	JMS10587	Finca Saboj, Tres Cruces	1400	15 May 1992	106
7	EA Mó	Finca Linda Vista, Pansal	1100	2009	130
8	Wilson	Hotel Ranchitos del Quetzal	1600	1 July 2013	101
9	JMS12277	Chilasco town	1875	28 July 2019	121
Izabal Department					
10	JMS10432	Cerro San Gil	950	15 July 1998	115
11	JMS10543	Cerro San Gil	950	15 July 1998	128
12	JMS10576	Cerro San Gil	950	3 May 1998	112
13	UVGC0010218	Cerro San Gil	950	July 1998	96
14	UVGC0010231	Cerro San Gil	950	26 June 1998	58
15	UVGC0010227	Cerro San Gil	950	July 1998	72
16	JMS10422	Mariscos town	10	15 July 1994	94
17	JMS10598	Mariscos town	10	15 July 1994	111
18	JMS10609	Mariscos town	10	15 July 1993	113
19	JMS10433	Mariscos town	10	17 July 1993	115
20	JMS10626	Finca Firmeza	450	10 July 1993	77
21	UVGC0010226	Finca Firmeza	600	7 June 2000	78
22	JMS10623	Finca Firmeza	600	5 June 2008	109
23	JMS10634	Finca Firmeza	600	5 June 2008	113
24	JMS10637	Finca Firmeza	900	10 July 1993	96
25	JMS10651	Finca Firmeza	900	3 July 1994	87
26	JMS9644	Finca Firmeza	900	3 July 1994	101
27	JMS10680	Finca Firmeza	900	3 July 1994	123
28	JMS10677	Finca Firmeza	900	3 July 1994	124
29	JMS10678	Finca Firmeza	900	3 July 1994	126
30	JMS9655	Finca Firmeza	900	3 July 1994	137
31	JMS12272	Finca Firmeza	900	3 July 1994	137
32	JMS10640	Finca Firmeza	950	15 April 2007	81
33	JMS10624	Finca Firmeza	950	10 May 2007	64
34	JMS10647	Finca Firmeza	950	10 May 2007	72
35	JMS10646	Finca Firmeza	950	10 May 2007	76

(Continued)

Appendix 1. (continued)

Specimen #	Code	Locality	Elevation (m)	Date	Length (mm)
36	JMS10636	Finca Firmeza	950	10 May 2007	88
37	JMS9647	Finca Firmeza	950	10 May 2007	93
38	JMS10648	Finca Firmeza	950	10 May 2007	95
39	JMS10650	Finca Firmeza	950	10 May 2007	100
40	JMS20639	Finca Firmeza	950	16 May 2007	89
41	JMS10653	Finca Firmeza	950	16 May 2007	124
42	JMS10633	Finca Firmeza	950	18 May 2007	61
43	JMS10635	Finca Firmeza	950	18 May 2007	77
44	JMS10632	Finca Firmeza	950	18 May 2007	115
45	JMS9677	Finca Firmeza	950	20 June 2007	104
46	JMS10409	Finca Firmeza	950	20 June 2007	115
47	JMS9688	Finca Firmeza	950	20 June 2007	123
48	JMS9700	Finca Firmeza	950	20 June 2007	131
49	JMS12271	Finca Firmeza	950	20 June 2007	133
50	JMS10625	Finca Firmeza	950	12 July 2007	88
51	JMS10619	Finca Firmeza	950	12 July 2007	90
52	JMS10608	Finca Firmeza	950	12 July 2007	91
53	JMS10630	Finca Firmeza	950	12 July 2007	92
54	JMS10408	Finca Firmeza	950	12 July 2007	124
55	JMS9666	Finca Firmeza	950	12 July 2007	105
56	JMS10586	Finca Firmeza	950	12 July 2007	107
57	JMS10597	Finca Firmeza	950	12 July 2007	110
58	JMS10575	Finca Firmeza	950	12 July 2007	116
59	JMS9699	Finca Firmeza	950	12 July 2007	116
60	JMS10643	Finca Firmeza	950	12 July 2007	116
61	JMS10644	Finca Firmeza	950	12 July 2007	116
62	JMS10667	Finca Firmeza	950	12 July 2007	117
63	JMS10652	Finca Firmeza	950	12 July 2007	121
64	JMS10629	Finca Firmeza	950	12 July 2007	121
65	JMS10641	Finca Firmeza	950	12 July 2007	122
66	JMS10622	Finca Firmeza	950	15 August 2007	70
67	JMS10621	Finca Firmeza	950	15 August 2007	72
68	JMS10553	Finca Firmeza	950	15 August 2007	86
69	JMS10638	Finca Firmeza	950	15 August 2007	91
70	JMS10564	Finca Firmeza	950	15 August 2007	95
71	JMS10649	Finca Firmeza	950	15 August 2007	97
72	JMS10627	Finca Firmeza	950	15 August 2007	98
73	JMS10628	Finca Firmeza	950	15 August 2007	100
74	JMS10642	Finca Firmeza	950	15 August 2007	118
75	WSUC	Finca Firmeza	950	21 July 2007	75

(Continued)

Appendix 1. (continued)

Specimen #	Code	Locality	Elevation (m)	Date	Length (mm)
76	WSUC	Finca Firmeza	950	21 July 2007	74
77	JMS9658	Finca Firmeza	1000	15 May 1997	125
78	JMS10679	Finca Firmeza	1000	8 May 1997	132
79	UVGC0010220	Finca Firmeza	1100	August 2000	91
80	UVGC0010229	Finca Firmeza	1100	7 June 2000	58
81	UVGC0010230	Finca Firmeza	1100	2 August 2000	70
82	UVGC0010259	Finca Firmeza	1100	August 2000	68
83	JMS10676	Finca Firmeza	1150	15 May 1996	123
84	JMS10682	Finca Firmeza	1150	26 June 1998	126
85	JMS10645	Finca Firmeza	1200	15 June 2006	110
86	MDPC	Reserva Hídrica y Forestal Sierra Caral	520	May 2015	110
87	MDPC	Reserva Hídrica y Forestal Sierra Caral	520	May 2015	125
88	MDPC	Reserva Hídrica y Forestal Sierra Caral	520	May 2015	120
89	MDPC	Reserva Hídrica y Forestal Sierra Caral	520	31 May 2014	80
90	MDPC	Reserva Hídrica y Forestal Sierra Caral	520	9 June 2019	140
91	MDPC	Reserva Hídrica y Forestal Sierra Caral	520	9 June 2019	75
92	UVGC0010222	Close to Negro Norte	1000	May 1997	88
93	UVGC0010212	Close to Negro Norte	1150	July 1994	126
94	UVGC0010213	Close to Negro Norte	1150	July 1994	114
95	UVGC0010215	Close to Negro Norte	1150	July 1994	125
96	UVGC0010216	Close to Negro Norte	1150	30 July 1997	118
97	UVGC0010221	Close to Negro Norte	1150	30 June 1997	83
98	UVGC0010223	Close to Negro Norte	1150	30 June 1997	78
99	UVGC0010224	Close to Negro Norte	1150	30 June 1997	76
100	UVGC0010225	Close to Negro Norte	1150	27 June 1998	68
101	UVGC0010258	Close to Negro Norte	1150	August 2000	64
102	UVGC0010228	Close to Negro Norte	1150	30 June 1977	58
103	UVGC0010214	Sierra de Caral	No data	June 1995	116
Quiché Department					
104	UVGC00102	Finca San Francisco	1200	February 2020	69
105	JMS12279	Cuatro Chorros, cerro Amay	1200	18 April 2024	108

Appendix 2. Female specimens of *Dynastes septentrionalis* examined in this study. Code: JMS = José Monzón Sierra; UVGC = Universidad del Valle de Guatemala Arthropod Collection; WSUC = Washington State University Collection; EA Mó = report from Edgar Alfredo Mó.

Specimen #	Code	Locality	Elevation (m)	Date	Length (mm)
Alta Verapaz Department					
1	JMS10509	Quixal	400	15 April 2007	61
2	JMS10510	Quixal	400	15 April 2007	64
3	UVGC0010232	Quixal	400	1998	58
4	UVGC0010245	San Cristobal Verapaz	No data	2 February 1995	59
Baja Verapaz Department					
5	EA Mó	Finca Linda Vista, Pansal	1100	2009	61
6	UVGC0010247	Finca Saboj, Tres Cruces	1300	June 1998	62
El Progreso Department					
7	JMS12282	San Lorenzo, above marble quarry	2033	9 August 2024	64
Huehuetenango Department					
8	JMS10603	Barillas, Unión las Palmas	1444	8 June 2010	61
9	UVGC0010248	Barillas, Nuevo San Mateo	1200	27 May 1998	67
10	JMS10488	Ixcansán	1600	26 July 2000	56
11	JMS10466	Ixcansán	1600	25 August 2004	61
Izabal Department					
12	UVGC0010237	Close to Río Zarco, above El Arenal	No data	4 April 1993	65
13	JMS10499	Cerro San Gil	950	4 June 1992	58
14	UVGC00102	Cerro San Gil	950	June 1998	62
15	UVGC00102	Cerro San Gil	950	July 1998	68
16	UVGC00102	Cerro San Gil	950	July 1998	59
17	UVGC00102	Cerro San Gil	950	26 June 1998	62
18	UVGC00102	Cerro San Gil	950	26 June 1998	61
19	UVGC00102	Finca Firmeza	700	July 2000	59
20	JMS10454	Finca Firmeza	950	26 October 2005	63
21	JMS10465	Finca Firmeza	950	26 October 2005	61
22	JMS10476	Finca Firmeza	950	16 May 2007	68
23	JMS10487	Finca Firmeza	950	18 June 2007	63
24	JMS10498	Finca Firmeza	950	18 June 2007	63
25	WSUC	Finca Firmeza	950	21 June 2007	60
26	WSUC	Finca Firmeza	950	21 June 2007	58
27	WSUC	Finca Firmeza	950	21 June 2007	53
28	WSUC	Finca Firmeza	950	21 June 2007	64
29	JMS12273	Reserva Hídrica y Forestal Sierra Caral	520	12 June 2018	66
30	JMS12274	Reserva Hídrica y Forestal Sierra Caral	520	12 June 2018	66

(Continued)

Appendix 2. (continued)

Specimen #	Code	Locality	Elevation (m)	Date	Length (mm)
31	UVGC00102	Close to Negro Norte	1000	May 1997	58
32	UVGC00102	Close to Negro Norte	1000	May 1997	59
33	UVGC00102	Close to Negro Norte	1150	27 June 1998	68
34	UVGC00102	Close to Negro Norte	1150	27 June 1998	62
35	UVGC00102	Close to Negro Norte	1150	April 1997	54
36	UVGC00102	Close to Negro Norte	1150	27 June 1998	54
37	UVGC00102	Sierra de Caral	1150	August 2000	58
38	UVGC00102	Sierra de Caral	1150	30 July 1997	58
Quiché Department					
39	UVGC0010238	Cerro Amay, Cuatro Chorros	1200	August 1998	61
40	JMS12276	Cerro Amay, Cuatro Chorros	1200	18 April 2024	66
Zacapa Department					
41	JMS10477	La Unión, above town	1540	13 August 1991	59

Appendix 3. Collecting locality information and geographic coordinates in decimal degrees.

	Locality	Municipality	Elevation (m)	Longitude	Latitude
Alta Verapaz Department					
1	Rubelsanto	Chisec	140	15.98862	-90.44670
2	Quixal	San Cristobal Verapaz	400	15.49136	-90.61040
3	San Cristóbal Verapaz	San Cristobal Verapaz	No data	No data	No data
Baja Verapaz Department					
4	Finca Saboj, Tres Cruces	Purulhá	1300	No data	No data
5	Finca Linda Vista, Pansal	Purulhá	1100	No data	No data
6	Hotel Ranchitos del Quetzal	Purulhá	1600	15.21575	-90.21909
El Progreso Department					
7	San Lorenzo, above marble quarry	San Agustín Acasaguastlán	2033	15.10496	-89.67692
Huehuetenango Department					
8	Unión Las Palmas	Santa Cruz Barillas	1440	15.931100	-91.29931
9	Nuevo San Mateo	Santa Cruz Barillas	1200	16.03181	-91.40343
Izabal Department					
10	Close to Río Zarco, above El Arenal	Los Amates	No data	No data	No data
11	Cerro San Gil	Puerto Barrios	950	15.67219	-88.69316
12	Mariscos town	Los Amates	10	15.42512	-89.07929
13	Finca Firmeza	Morales	450	15.39230	-88.72337
14	Finca Firmeza	Morales	600	15.38560	-88.71675
15	Finca Firmeza	Morales	700	15.37987	-88.71265
16	Finca Firmeza, logging camp	Morales	900-950	15.379304	-88.69477
17	Finca Firmeza	Morales	1000	15.37537	-88.69433
18	Finca Firmeza	Morales	1150	15.36481	-88.69472
19	Finca Firmeza	Morales	1200	15.35619	-88.68238
20	Reserva Hídrica y Forestal Sierra Caral	Morales	520	15.40702	-88.69622
21	Close to Negro Norte (= Finca Firmeza)	Morales	1000	15.37537	-88.69433
22	Close to Negro Norte (= Finca Firmeza)	Morales	1150	15.36481	-88.69472
23	Sierra Caral (= Finca Firmeza)	Morales	No data	No data	No data
Quiché Department					
24	Finca San Francisco	San Juan Cotzal	1200	15.49511	-90.85873
25	Cuatro Chorros, Cerro Amay	Uspantán	1200	15.51350	-90.76608
Zacapa Department					
26	La Unión, above town	La Unión	1540	14.94661	-89.27763